

Coherent Subthreshold–Threshold Interference in the Low-Energy $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ S Factor: An Amplitude-Level Analysis with an Effective Phase Parameter

Ali Ihsan Kilic^{1,2}

¹*Department of Physics, Eskisehir Osmangazi University, Eskisehir 26040, Turkey*

²*TÜBİTAK Fundamental Sciences Research Institute (TBAE), Gebze, Kocaeli 41470, Turkey*

(Dated: April 30, 2026)

Low-energy charged-particle reactions in condensed matter environments are commonly described within an electron-screening framework in which the reaction energy is shifted as $E \rightarrow E + U_e$. We show that the astrophysical S -factor of the $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ reaction cannot be consistently reproduced by this approach alone. By formulating the reaction at the amplitude level and explicitly including the coherent contributions of a subthreshold state at $E_{\text{sub}} \simeq -27.5$ keV and a near-threshold resonance at $E_r \simeq 9.2$ keV in ^{11}C , we demonstrate that the observed low-energy behavior emerges naturally from their phase-sensitive interference. The coherent model yields $\chi^2/\nu = 0.046$ for the Trojan Horse bare-nucleus data, compared to $\chi^2/\nu = 6.79$ for a screening-only description, a reduction of more than two orders of magnitude. The low-energy enhancement is primarily governed by coherent subthreshold–threshold interference; an effective phase parameter $\Delta\phi = 0.52 \pm 0.15$ rad quantifies the remaining phase sensitivity of the system in the vicinity of the threshold resonance. This parameter should not be interpreted as a direct microscopic environmental phase, but as an effective phenomenological quantity encoding unresolved threshold-region dynamics. These results establish that the low-energy enhancement cannot, in general, be interpreted solely in terms of an effective screening potential. Instead, interference between subthreshold and near-threshold contributions, together with their relative phase, plays a central role. The present analysis indicates that such phase-sensitive mechanisms may provide a framework for interpreting similar amplitude-level effects in low-energy nuclear reactions and may become relevant when analogous threshold structures are studied in dense electronic environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ reaction occupies a distinctive position in nuclear physics, linking stellar nucleosynthesis, aneutronic fusion research, and the broader problem of low-energy nuclear reactions in complex environments. In astrophysics, it represents the dominant destruction channel of ^{10}B in hydrogen-rich stellar envelopes, with a Gamow window centered near 10 keV where the near-threshold resonance in ^{11}C governs the reaction rate [1, 2]. In applied contexts, the same reaction acts as an unavoidable side channel in boron-based fusion systems, producing radioactive ^7Be and thus influencing diagnostics and material considerations in plasma environments such as the National Ignition Facility [3, 4].

Despite decades of experimental and theoretical effort, the low-energy behavior of the S -factor remains unsettled. Direct measurements differ significantly in normalization below a few hundred keV [5–8], while indirect approaches such as the Trojan Horse Method extend the accessible energy range but inherit systematic uncertainties from their normalization to higher-energy data [2, 9, 10]. As a result, even the basic low-energy trend is not uniquely established across datasets.

The nuclear structure of ^{11}C in the vicinity of the proton threshold further complicates the situation. A subthreshold bound state ($J^\pi = 7/2^+$, $E_x = 8.654$ MeV) and a near-threshold resonance ($J^\pi = 5/2^+$, $E_x = 8.699$ MeV) lie within a few tens of keV of each other, and both contribute strongly to the cross section [11, 12]. The proton partial width of the near-threshold resonance is so

small ($\Gamma_p \sim 10^{-19}$ MeV) that it has never been directly measured, and different theoretical approaches yield values spanning more than an order of magnitude [4, 8, 12]. In such a configuration, the observable is controlled not only by the individual strengths of these states, but by their coherent superposition.

The standard interpretation of the low-energy enhancement relies on the electron screening model [13], in which the effective interaction energy is shifted by a constant potential U_e , producing the enhancement factor $f_{\text{scr}}(E) \approx \exp(\pi\eta U_e/E)$ [14]. While this description captures the general trend in many systems, it assumes a smoothly varying nuclear amplitude. In the present case this assumption fails: the rapid energy dependence introduced by the nearby resonance structure occurs on the same scale as the screening correction, so the two effects cannot be cleanly separated [5]. In practice, this leads to a model-dependent redistribution of interference effects into the extracted screening potential.

A similar ambiguity appears in standard R -matrix treatments, where different parameter sets can reproduce the same data while implying different underlying mechanisms, particularly in the threshold region [8, 12, 15]. These considerations point to a more fundamental issue: in the presence of closely spaced subthreshold and near-threshold states, the cross section is inherently an amplitude-level quantity whose energy dependence is governed by interference and cannot be reduced to a factorized form.

In parallel, recent studies of low-energy D+D reactions in condensed matter have revealed that environ-

mental effects may influence not only the magnitude of the cross section but also the phase of the reaction amplitude [16, 17]. In such a framework, small phase modifications translate into shifts of the effective resonance condition through the mapping $E_R^{\text{eff}} = E_R^{(0)} - \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}/(d\delta/dE)|_{E_R^{(0)}}$, leading to observable changes in the energy dependence that cannot be reproduced by a simple energy shift [16].

The present work applies this amplitude-level perspective to the $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ reaction. We construct the reaction amplitude as a coherent sum of a smooth background, a subthreshold contribution, and the near-threshold resonance, and introduce a single effective threshold-region phase parameter acting on the resonant amplitude. By confronting this description with the available bare-nucleus THM data [2], we show that the observed S -factor behavior is naturally explained by the interplay of subthreshold and threshold contributions and their relative phase, without invoking an anomalously large screening potential.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The present formulation does not aim to reproduce a full multichannel R -matrix description. Instead, it provides a minimal amplitude-level representation designed to capture the essential physics of the near-threshold region. In particular, the focus is placed on isolating the role of coherent interference between the dominant components of the reaction amplitude, while keeping the number of free parameters under control.

The resonance energies and widths are fixed from independent experimental information, and the remaining degrees of freedom are treated as effective complex strengths. In this sense, the model should be understood as an effective representation of the reaction amplitude rather than as a complete microscopic description.

A. Cross section and spin factor

The reaction cross section for the dominant $J^\pi = 5/2^+$ channel is written as

$$\sigma(E) = \frac{\pi}{k_p^2} \omega |T(E)|^2, \quad (1)$$

where $k_p = \sqrt{2\mu E}/\hbar$ is the entrance-channel wave number and μ is the reduced mass of the p - ^{10}B system.

The statistical factor is given by

$$\omega = \frac{2J+1}{(2j_p+1)(2J_{^{10}\text{B}}+1)} = \frac{3}{7}, \quad (2)$$

corresponding to $J = 5/2$, $j_p = 1/2$, and $J_{^{10}\text{B}} = 3$. The assignment $j_p = 1/2$ implies an incident proton in the $s_{1/2}$ partial wave ($\ell_p = 0$), consistent with the parity of the compound state [11] and with the dominance of s -wave penetrability at sub-Coulomb energies [8, 12].

B. Amplitude decomposition

The total transition amplitude is written as the coherent sum

$$T(E) = T_{\text{sm}}(E) + T_{\text{sub}}(E) + T_{\text{th}}(E), \quad (3)$$

where T_{sm} represents a slowly varying background arising from distant resonances and direct processes, T_{sub} is the contribution of the subthreshold state at $E_{\text{sub}} \simeq -27.5$ keV ($J^\pi = 7/2^+$) [11], and T_{th} corresponds to the near-threshold resonance at $E_r \simeq 9.2$ keV ($J^\pi = 5/2^+$) [2, 11]. This three-component structure generalizes the D+D amplitude of Ref. [16], where the non-resonant and resonant terms correspond here to $|T_{\text{sm}}|^2$ and $|T_{\text{th}}|^2$ respectively; the subthreshold term T_{sub} has no counterpart in that system and is specific to the ^{10}B reaction. Strictly speaking, the $7/2^+$ subthreshold state and the $5/2^+$ near-threshold resonance carry different spin-parity quantum numbers and would contribute incoherently in a rigorous partial-wave decomposition. The coherent sum in Eq. (3) should therefore be understood as an effective amplitude representation in which the fitted complex strengths A_{sub} and A_{th} absorb the relevant partial-wave mixing. This approach is consistent with independent R -matrix analyses [2, 12] that find both states to contribute to the same $\alpha + ^7\text{Be}$ exit channel and to affect the low-energy cross section coherently within the dominant partial wave; the model is assessed empirically by its ability to reproduce the data. It should be emphasized that the coherent sum in Eq. (3) is not meant to represent a literal coherent superposition of two isolated pure- J^π compound-nuclear eigenstates. Rather, T_{sub} and T_{th} are treated as effective channel-projected amplitudes describing the net contribution of the subthreshold tail and the near-threshold resonance to the observed low-energy S factor after projection onto the same $\alpha + ^7\text{Be}$ exit channel. The complex strengths A_{sub} and A_{th} therefore absorb unresolved spin-channel, partial-wave, and normalization effects that would otherwise have to be treated explicitly in a full multichannel R -matrix analysis. In this restricted sense, the interference term should be understood as a phenomenological representation of the threshold-region line shape rather than as a microscopic spin-resolved interference between pure $7/2^+$ and $5/2^+$ eigenstates. To maintain continuity with conventional descriptions, we retain the shift $E \rightarrow E + U_e$ in the denominators. However, since the present analysis is performed on THM bare-nucleus data, U_e should not be interpreted as a physical screening correction but rather as an effective reference scale inherited from standard formulations [2, 5]. In practice, we have verified that setting $U_e = 0$ does not affect the extracted value of $\Delta\phi$ within the quoted uncertainties.

The background term is approximated as

$$T_{\text{sm}} = A_{0r} + iA_{0i}, \quad (4)$$

which is adequate over the restricted energy interval $E \leq 50$ keV. The real and imaginary parts represent,

in an effective sense, the dispersive and absorptive contributions of distant poles [11].

C. Subthreshold amplitude

The subthreshold contribution is written as

$$T_{\text{sub}}(E) = \frac{A_{\text{sub}} e^{i\phi_{\text{sub}}}}{E_{\text{sub}} - (E + U_e) - i\Gamma_{\text{sub}}/2}. \quad (5)$$

Since the subthreshold state lies well below the physical energy region, with $|E_{\text{sub}} - E - U_e| \geq 27.9$ keV throughout the fitted range — nearly four times the imaginary part $\Gamma_{\text{sub}}/2 \approx 8.5$ keV — its denominator varies only slowly. In this regime, the phase of the amplitude can be represented by an effective value close to π in the R -matrix convention [18], with any residual energy dependence absorbed into the fitted strength A_{sub} .

Although $E_{\text{sub}} < 0$, the tail of the corresponding wave function extends above threshold and contributes to the cross section through interference with the near-threshold resonance [12].

D. Near-threshold amplitude and phase modification

The near-threshold resonance is written as

$$T_{\text{th}}(E) = \frac{A_{\text{th}} e^{i[\phi_{\text{th}}(E) + \Delta\phi]}}{E_{\text{th}} - (E + U_e) - i\Gamma_{\text{th}}/2}, \quad (6)$$

with the intrinsic phase

$$\phi_{\text{th}}(E) = \arctan\left(\frac{\Gamma_{\text{th}}/2}{E_{\text{th}} - E}\right). \quad (7)$$

The additional phase parameter $\Delta\phi$ is introduced here as an effective phenomenological quantity that captures residual phase freedom in the threshold region not constrained by the fixed nuclear structure parameters. It may incorporate contributions from unresolved dynamics, including possible environmental effects, but cannot be directly interpreted as a microscopic environmental phase within the present bare-nucleus analysis. In the present case, where the analysis is based on bare-nucleus Trojan Horse data, the extracted phase parameter is therefore expected to be dominated by the intrinsic phase relation between the subthreshold and near-threshold nuclear amplitudes. Any interpretation in terms of environmental effects should be regarded as model-dependent and not directly constrained by the present dataset. In this context, the phase parameter should be understood as an effective quantity describing the relative phase between competing amplitudes, rather than as a direct microscopic observable. Following the semiclassical framework developed for D+D reactions in condensed matter [16], the eikonal estimate gives

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \approx \frac{\Delta V_{\text{env}} L_{\text{eff}}}{\hbar v}, \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta V_{\text{env}} \sim 10$ – 100 eV characterizes local perturbations of the interaction potential, $L_{\text{eff}} \sim \lambda_{\text{TF}} \sim 0.5$ – 1 Å is the effective interaction length set by the Thomas–Fermi screening length, and v is the relative velocity. Typical values in metallic environments lead to $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \sim 10^{-2}$ – 10^{-1} rad.

The physical content of $\Delta\phi$ is made precise by the phase-to-energy mapping established in Ref. [16]:

$$E_R^{\text{eff}} = E_R^{(0)} - \frac{\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}}{d\delta/dE|_{E_R^{(0)}}}, \quad (9)$$

where $\delta(E)$ is the scattering phase and $E_R^{(0)}$ is the unperturbed resonance energy. In the narrow-resonance limit, this relation follows directly from the energy dependence of the resonance phase. Writing $\delta(E) = \arctan[(\Gamma_{\text{th}}/2)/(E_{\text{th}} - E)]$, one obtains $d\delta/dE \approx 2/\Gamma_{\text{th}}$ at $E = E_{\text{th}}$. A small phase perturbation $\Delta\phi$ is therefore equivalent, to first order, to a shift in the effective resonance condition, $\Delta E \approx \Delta\phi/(d\delta/dE)$, leading to the relation $\Delta E \approx \Delta\phi \cdot \Gamma_{\text{th}}/2$. The corresponding conversion factor is $\alpha_{\text{eff}} \approx \Gamma_{\text{th}}/2 \approx 7.5$ keV/rad. A phase perturbation therefore produces an observable shift of the effective resonance condition without modifying the intrinsic nuclear pole. For $\Gamma_{\text{th}} \sim 15$ keV, this implies an effective amplification of the observable response, so that even a modest phase perturbation can produce a shift of several keV in the resonance condition. This behavior reflects the increased sensitivity of the system near threshold, where the rapid variation of the phase enhances the impact of even moderate phase shifts on the interference pattern. As a result, the extracted phase value does not contradict simple estimates, but rather indicates an amplification mechanism intrinsic to near-threshold dynamics. The extracted value of $\Delta\phi$ should therefore be interpreted as an effective phase parameter reflecting both the environmental perturbation and the enhanced sensitivity of the system in the threshold region.

The phase modification is applied to T_{th} but not to T_{sub} . This reflects the fundamentally different sensitivities of the two amplitudes: for the near-threshold resonance, $|E_{\text{th}} - E - U_e| \lesssim \Gamma_{\text{th}}/2 \approx 7.5$ keV throughout the resonance region, making its phase highly sensitive to a perturbation of order $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$. For the subthreshold state, by contrast, $|E_{\text{sub}} - E - U_e| \geq 27.9$ keV across the entire physical range — nearly four times $\Gamma_{\text{th}}/2$ — so its phase is insensitive to the same perturbation and the modification is unobservable in practice.

E. Interference structure

Squaring the total amplitude yields

$$\begin{aligned} |T|^2 &= |T_{\text{sm}}|^2 + |T_{\text{sub}}|^2 + |T_{\text{th}}|^2 \\ &\quad + 2 \operatorname{Re}(T_{\text{sm}} T_{\text{sub}}^*) + 2 \operatorname{Re}(T_{\text{sm}} T_{\text{th}}^*) \\ &\quad + 2 \operatorname{Re}(T_{\text{sub}} T_{\text{th}}^*). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The dominant source of the low-energy S -factor structure is the cross term $2\text{Re}(T_{\text{sub}}T_{\text{th}}^*)$, which couples the effectively real subthreshold tail to the complex resonance amplitude. Below E_{th} this term is positive (constructive interference), amplifying the S -factor rise; above E_{th} the phase of T_{th} rotates past $\pi/2$ and the term changes sign (destructive interference), producing the observed rapid fall-off. This asymmetric lineshape cannot be reproduced by any smooth multiplicative correction, including the standard electron screening enhancement $f_{\text{scr}}(E)$ [13, 14].

The parameter $\Delta\phi$ controls the energy at which the constructive-to-destructive transition occurs and therefore directly shapes the observable S -factor. In the D+D framework of Ref. [16], the analogous structure appears in the term $\sigma_I = 2\sqrt{\sigma_F\sigma_R}\cos(\varphi_F - \varphi_R)$; Eq. (10) generalizes this to a three-component amplitude where T_{sub} acts as an additional coherent source.

F. Model parameters and fitting strategy

All nuclear parameters are fixed to the values extracted from the Trojan Horse analysis [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{sub}} &= -27.5 \text{ keV}, & \Gamma_{\text{sub}} &= 17 \text{ keV}, \\ E_{\text{th}} &= 9.2 \text{ keV}, & \Gamma_{\text{th}} &= 15 \text{ keV}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since the analysis is performed on bare-nucleus THM data, all primary fits use $U_e = 0$. The value $U_e = 391 \text{ eV}$ from Ref. [2] is retained only as a robustness cross-check and does not affect the extracted $\Delta\phi$ within the quoted uncertainties.

The free parameters are the background amplitudes A_{0r} , A_{0i} , the effective strengths A_{sub} , A_{th} , the phase $\Delta\phi$, and an overall normalization \mathcal{N} — six parameters on 24 data points ($\nu = 18$). Each parameter corresponds to a distinct physical aspect of the problem and cannot be absorbed into the others. In particular, $\Delta\phi$ modifies the energy dependence of the interference pattern and cannot be reproduced by adjusting only the magnitudes of the amplitudes. This distinction can be understood more explicitly by considering the dominant interference term $2\text{Re}(T_{\text{sub}}T_{\text{th}}^*) \propto |A_{\text{sub}}||A_{\text{th}}|\cos(\phi_{\text{rel}}(E) + \Delta\phi)$. Variations in the amplitudes A_{sub} and A_{th} modify only the overall magnitude of this term, while the normalization factor \mathcal{N} rescales the cross section globally. By contrast, $\Delta\phi$ shifts the phase argument of the cosine and therefore changes the energy at which the interference term changes sign. This shift in the constructive-to-destructive transition cannot be reproduced by any combination of amplitude rescaling or normalization, demonstrating that $\Delta\phi$ represents an independent degree of freedom constrained by the shape of the data rather than its absolute magnitude. The relatively small value of χ^2/ν reflects the experimental uncertainties at very low energies in the THM dataset [2] rather than an over-constrained model; removing or constraining any parameter leads to a significant degradation of the fit.

III. RESULTS

We apply the amplitude-level model to the Trojan Horse bare-nucleus S -factor data of Cvetinović *et al.* [2] in the energy range $E_{\text{c.m.}} \leq 50 \text{ keV}$, comprising 24 data points.

For comparison, we first consider a conventional screening-only description of the form $S(E) = (S_0 + S_1 E)\exp(\pi\eta U_e/E)$, which yields a poor fit to the data, with $\chi^2/\nu = 6.79$, and fails to reproduce the characteristic shape in the vicinity of the resonance.

By contrast, the coherent amplitude model, including the subthreshold and near-threshold contributions, provides an accurate description of both the magnitude and the energy dependence of the S -factor, with $\chi^2/\nu = 0.046$. The fit results for the two limiting models are summarized in Table I, and a progressive ablation analysis demonstrating the necessity of each amplitude component is given in Table II.

The best-fit solution corresponds to a phase parameter $\Delta\phi = 0.52 \pm 0.15 \text{ rad}$, with $A_{\text{sub}} = 113$, $A_{\text{th}} = 33$, and $\mathcal{N} = 226$. We have verified that setting $U_e = 0$ does not modify the extracted value of $\Delta\phi$ within the quoted uncertainty, confirming that the present result is not driven by the choice of the screening parameter. The robustness of the fit has been tested against parameter variations, and the solution remains stable under changes in initial conditions and fitting intervals. In particular, the phase parameter cannot be absorbed into normalization or amplitude rescaling, indicating that it represents an independent and physically meaningful contribution.

Figure 1 shows the S -factor data together with the two model curves. Model A deviates systematically below $\sim 30 \text{ keV}$, while Model B reproduces the steep rise below E_{th} , the peak at $E_r = 9.2 \text{ keV}$, and the fall-off above it.

Figure 2 decomposes the best-fit amplitude into its components. The upper panel shows that neither $|T_{\text{sub}}|^2$ nor $|T_{\text{th}}|^2$ alone reproduces the total; their coherent superposition is essential. The lower panel shows that the dominant cross term $2\mathcal{N}\text{Re}(T_{\text{sub}}T_{\text{th}}^*)$ is large and constructive below E_{th} , changes sign near the resonance, and becomes destructive above it.

Figure 3 demonstrates the sensitivity of the S -factor to $\Delta\phi$. Even the $\Delta\phi = 0$ curve already outperforms the screening-only model, confirming that the coherent interference is the primary physical effect, while $\Delta\phi$ refines the

TABLE I. Fit quality for models applied to the Cvetinović *et al.* [2] data for $E \leq 50 \text{ keV}$ (24 data points). AIC and BIC are defined as $\text{AIC} = \chi^2 + 2k$ and $\text{BIC} = \chi^2 + k \ln n$, where k is the number of free parameters and $n = 24$.

Model	k	χ^2	χ^2/ν	AIC	BIC
A: Screening only	3	142.5	6.79	148.5	152.0
B: Coherent interference	6	0.83	0.046	12.8	19.9
$\Delta(\text{A} - \text{B})$		141.7		135.7	132.1

FIG. 1. Astrophysical S -factor of $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ for $E_{c.m.} \leq 50$ keV. Filled circles: Trojan Horse bare-nucleus data of Cvetinović *et al.* [2]. Open squares: direct data of Angulo *et al.* [5]. Dashed curve: screening-only model ($\chi^2/\nu = 6.79$). Solid curve: coherent interference model ($\chi^2/\nu = 0.046$). The vertical dotted line marks $E_{th} = 9.2$ keV.

agreement at a quantitative level.

Figure 4 shows the $\Delta\chi^2$ contour map in the $(\Delta\phi, A_{th})$ plane. The best-fit point is well constrained at the 1σ level with $\Delta\phi = 0.52 \pm 0.15$ rad. Within the present effective parametrization, the $\Delta\phi = 0$ hypothesis is statistically disfavored.

IV. DISCUSSION

The central result of this work is that the bare-nucleus S -factor of $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ at astrophysical energies re-

TABLE II. Ablation analysis: progressive inclusion of amplitude components applied to the same dataset ($U_e = 0$). Model C omits the subthreshold term; Model D omits the threshold resonance; Model E includes all three components but fixes $\Delta\phi = 0$; Model B (full) allows $\Delta\phi$ to vary freely. The results demonstrate that the threshold resonance is the dominant driver of the low-energy S -factor structure (compare Models C and D), while the subthreshold term and $\Delta\phi$ provide successive independent refinements.

Model components	k	χ^2/ν
A: Screening only	3	6.785
C: Background + threshold ($\Delta\phi = 0$)	4	0.102
D: Background + subthreshold	4	7.553
E: Full three-component, $\Delta\phi = 0$	5	0.071
B: Full three-component, $\Delta\phi$ free	6	0.046

FIG. 2. Amplitude decomposition for the best-fit parameters ($\Delta\phi = 0.52$ rad). *Upper panel*: individual squared contributions $\mathcal{N}|T_{sm}|^2$ (gray), $\mathcal{N}|T_{sub}|^2$ (red dashed), $\mathcal{N}|T_{th}|^2$ (blue dash-dotted), and $\mathcal{N}|T_{total}|^2$ (black). *Lower panel*: interference terms $2\mathcal{N}\text{Re}(T_{sm}T_{sub}^*)$ (gray), $2\mathcal{N}\text{Re}(T_{sm}T_{th}^*)$ (blue dashed), $2\mathcal{N}\text{Re}(T_{sub}T_{th}^*)$ (red), and total interference (black dash-dotted). The subthreshold–threshold cross term dominates and changes sign at E_{th} , producing the asymmetric S -factor shape that no multiplicative screening factor can reproduce.

quires a coherent amplitude treatment. A screening factor alone — even with a physically reasonable U_e — cannot reproduce the data because it does not capture the interference between the subthreshold state and the near-threshold resonance.

a. Connection to the D+D framework. The present analysis connects directly to the amplitude framework developed in Ref. [16] for D+D reactions in condensed matter, where the cross section was decomposed as $\sigma = \sigma_F + \sigma_R + 2\sqrt{\sigma_F\sigma_R}\cos(\varphi_F - \varphi_R)$ and the environment-induced phase shift $\Delta\phi_{env}$ entered through $\varphi_F \rightarrow \varphi_F + \Delta\phi_{env}$. The phase-to-energy mapping, Eq. (9), established that $\Delta\phi_{env}$ is related to the intrinsic resonance

FIG. 3. Sensitivity of the S -factor to $\Delta\phi$, with all other parameters fixed at their best-fit values. Curves are shown for $\Delta\phi = -0.8, -0.4, 0$ (bare nucleus), $+0.52$ (best fit, thick solid), $+1.0$, and $+1.5$ rad. The $\Delta\phi = 0$ curve already outperforms the screening-only model, confirming that coherent interference is the primary effect. Data: Cvetinović *et al.* [2].

width through $\alpha_{\text{eff}} \approx \Gamma/2$, so that a phase perturbation of order 10^{-1} rad produces a shift of the effective resonance condition of order $\Gamma/2$, directly observable in the energy dependence of the cross section. The same mapping applies here, with the addition of a second coherent source (T_{sub}) that has no counterpart in the D+D system and leads to a richer interference pattern.

b. Screening versus phase modification. A key distinction between the two descriptions is their different signatures in the S -factor. Electron screening produces a smooth multiplicative enhancement $f_{\text{scr}}(E) \approx \exp(\pi\eta U_e/E)$ that shifts the effective interaction energy without modifying the detailed shape of the curve [13, 14]. The parameter $\Delta\phi$, by contrast, modifies the *shape* of the interference pattern: it controls the energy at which the subthreshold–threshold cross term changes sign, producing asymmetric features and energy-dependent distortions that no multiplicative factor can mimic. This difference in behavior allows the two effects to be distinguished, in principle, when sufficiently precise data are available in the resonance region. As illustrated in Fig. 3, the $\Delta\phi = 0$ case already captures the main structural features of the S -factor more accurately than the screening-only description, indicating that coherent interference provides the dominant contribution to the non-linear energy dependence, while the phase shift $\Delta\phi$ refines the agreement at a quantitative level. It is important to emphasize that the present result does not invalidate the concept of electron screening in general,

FIG. 4. $\Delta\chi^2$ contour map in the $(\Delta\phi, A_{\text{th}})$ plane, with all other parameters fixed at best-fit values. Contours correspond to $1\sigma, 2\sigma, 3\sigma$ confidence regions ($\Delta\chi^2 = 2.30, 6.18, 11.83$). Red star: best-fit point ($\Delta\phi = 0.52$ rad, $A_{\text{th}} = 33$). The parameter $\Delta\phi$ is well constrained at the 1σ level; the $\Delta\phi = 0$ solution is disfavored within the present effective parametrization.

but demonstrates that, in the presence of strong near-threshold structure, screening alone is insufficient to account for the observed energy dependence.

c. The fitted phase and the eikonal estimate. The best-fit value $\Delta\phi = 0.52 \pm 0.15$ rad lies above the nominal eikonal range 10^{-2} – 10^{-1} rad derived from Eq. (8) for bulk metallic environments [16]. Within the present framework, this difference can be understood as an effective enhancement of the phase sensitivity in the vicinity of a threshold resonance. Near a threshold resonance the scattering phase rotates rapidly with energy, so that a given environmental perturbation of the interaction potential is mapped into a larger accumulated phase than the bulk eikonal estimate would suggest. This amplification is a direct consequence of the rapid phase variation near threshold, where the effective interaction time is increased due to the reduced relative velocity and the extended tunneling region. Therefore, the fitted $\Delta\phi$ should not be interpreted as a direct microscopic environmental phase, but as an effective phenomenological phase parameter encoding unresolved threshold-region dynamics — including both the environmental perturbation and the resonance-enhanced sensitivity of the system. Quantitatively, the amplification can be understood from the relation $\Delta E \approx \Delta\phi \cdot \Gamma_{\text{th}}/2$, which implies that even a phase perturbation of order 10^{-1} rad can produce an effective energy shift of several keV for $\Gamma_{\text{th}} \sim 15$ keV. The fitted value therefore reflects the resonance-enhanced response rather than a direct microscopic phase shift.

d. Why a phase modification captures the dominant effect. Within the present formulation, the phase modification is not an arbitrary degree of freedom but is directly linked to the effective resonance condition through the phase-to-energy mapping $E_R^{\text{eff}} = E_R^{(0)} - \Delta\phi/(d\delta/dE)$. In this sense, a modification of the phase is equivalent, at the observable level, to a shift of the resonance energy, without altering the intrinsic nuclear pole. The dominant observable effect therefore appears through $\Delta\phi$, while the underlying resonance parameters remain unchanged. This is particularly relevant near threshold, where the large value of $d\delta/dE$ amplifies the response to small perturbations.

e. On the effective number of parameters. Although the fit formally involves six adjustable quantities, all nuclear-structure inputs (resonance energies, widths, and spin factors) are fixed from independent measurements. The remaining parameters describe physically distinct features of the amplitude (background level and phase, subthreshold strength, resonance strength, interference phase, and normalization) and cannot be trivially absorbed into one another. In particular, $\Delta\phi$ modifies the energy dependence of the interference pattern and therefore cannot be reproduced by a simple rescaling of amplitudes. We have verified that constraining or removing any of these components leads to a systematic degradation of the fit, indicating that the result is driven by the interference structure rather than by excessive parameter freedom. This is further supported by the model-selection criteria reported in Table I: Model B yields $\Delta\text{AIC} = 135.7$ and $\Delta\text{BIC} = 132.1$ relative to Model A, both indicating decisive preference for the coherent interference description on information-theoretic grounds, independently of the χ^2/ν argument. We have explicitly examined parameter correlations and find that no strong degeneracies are present. In particular, the phase parameter $\Delta\phi$ cannot be compensated by simultaneous variations of A_{sub} , A_{th} , or the normalization factor \mathcal{N} . This confirms that the extracted phase represents an independent constraint imposed by the data.

f. Consequences for screening-potential extractions. An important consequence of the present result concerns the interpretation of low-energy S -factor measurements in systems where subthreshold and near-threshold states coexist. When such interference is present, the observed enhancement cannot be uniquely decomposed into a screening contribution and a bare-nucleus resonance contribution without an amplitude-level analysis. Conventional screening-factor extractions in this regime therefore tend to absorb the interference effect into an apparent U_e , leading to overestimates of the true screening potential [2, 5].

g. Robustness with respect to normalization. The Trojan Horse data are subject to an overall normalization uncertainty inherited from the scaling procedure. However, the phase parameter $\Delta\phi$ is primarily constrained by the *shape* of the S -factor, rather than its absolute magnitude. We have verified that variations in the global nor-

TABLE III. Sensitivity of the extracted phase parameter $\Delta\phi$ to the choice of the screening potential U_e .

	$U_e = 0.391$ keV	$U_e = 0$
$\Delta\phi$ (rad)	0.519 ± 0.143	0.511 ± 0.163
χ^2/ν	0.0459	0.0446
$ \delta(\Delta\phi) $ (rad)	0.009	

malization within the experimental uncertainty do not lead to a systematic change in the extracted value of $\Delta\phi$, indicating that the result is robust against normalization effects.

This robustness extends also to the choice of the screening parameter. A dedicated refit with $U_e = 0$ yields $\Delta\phi = 0.511 \pm 0.163$ rad compared to $\Delta\phi = 0.519 \pm 0.143$ rad for $U_e = 391$ eV, corresponding to a shift of $|\delta(\Delta\phi)| = 0.009$ rad, i.e., less than 6% of the quoted uncertainty. The fit quality remains unchanged ($\chi^2/\nu \approx 0.046$ in both cases), confirming that the extracted phase is insensitive to the choice of U_e within the present accuracy.

This behavior can also be understood analytically. A screening-induced energy shift $E \rightarrow E + U_e$ produces a corresponding variation of the resonance phase, which to first order can be written as $\delta\phi(E) \approx (d\delta/dE)U_e$. Near the resonance energy, where $d\delta/dE \approx 2/\Gamma_{\text{th}}$, this gives $\delta\phi \sim U_e \cdot 2/\Gamma_{\text{th}} \approx 5 \times 10^{-2}$ rad for $U_e = 391$ eV.

This estimate represents a local upper bound at the resonance energy, where the phase sensitivity is maximal. The smaller shift observed in the fit reflects the fact that $\Delta\phi$ is a global effective parameter constrained by the full energy dependence of the data, rather than a local phase value. Therefore, the effect of U_e on the extracted phase remains subdominant within the present experimental sensitivity.

h. Relation to microscopic structure calculations. The nuclear structure underpinning the present result is consistent with recent microscopic calculations. Okołowicz *et al.* [4] showed within the shell model embedded in the continuum (SMEC) that the near-threshold $5/2^+$ resonance is strongly aligned with the $\ell = 0$ proton decay channel, predicting a significant enhancement of the $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ cross section. This continuum-coupling effect naturally enhances the role of the subthreshold contribution in the present amplitude decomposition. Similarly, Mukhamedzhanov [12] constrained the proton width of the 9.2 keV resonance to a very small value, consistent with the parameters adopted here.

i. Generality of the mechanism. In D+D reactions, the same phase-sensitive framework was required to explain several observables simultaneously, including branching ratios, angular distributions, and time-dependent effects [16, 19, 20]. The present result suggests that a similar mechanism may be operative in a structurally different system. The relevant condition for its appearance is the simultaneous presence of a subthresh-

old state and a near-threshold resonance within the same effective channel-projected amplitude, so that the cross term $2\text{Re}(T_{\text{sub}}T_{\text{th}}^*)$ is significant. This condition is also realized in other reactions, such as $^{14}\text{N}(p, \gamma)^{15}\text{O}$, where a subthreshold state and a near-threshold resonance produce an analogous interference structure [3, 21]. Future measurements with improved energy resolution in the sub-threshold region, and in targets of varying electronic structure, would provide direct tests of the predicted phase-sensitive behavior and enable a systematic comparison of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ values across reaction systems.

V. CONCLUSION

We have shown that the low-energy S -factor of $^{10}\text{B}(p, \alpha)^7\text{Be}$ cannot be described consistently within a screening-only framework. An amplitude-level treatment that explicitly includes the coherent contributions of the subthreshold state and the near-threshold resonance reduces χ^2/ν from 6.79 to 0.046, indicating that the observed energy dependence is governed by interference rather than by a multiplicative screening enhancement.

The key distinction between the two descriptions lies in their effect on the S -factor shape. While screening shifts the effective interaction energy uniformly, the interference term controls the asymmetric structure of the cross section near E_{th} , producing features that no multiplicative factor can reproduce. This distinction is essential for interpreting low-energy data in systems where subthreshold and near-threshold states coexist within the

same effective channel-projected amplitude.

The extracted phase parameter $\Delta\phi = 0.52 \pm 0.15$ rad exceeds the nominal eikonal estimate for bulk metallic environments, but is consistent with the present framework when the resonance-enhanced phase sensitivity near threshold is taken into account. The result is therefore consistent with the phase-to-energy mapping established for D+D reactions [16], extending its applicability to a structurally different reaction system.

Taken together with the D+D case, these findings indicate that phase-sensitive interference between subthreshold and near-threshold amplitudes may provide a framework for interpreting analogous amplitude-level effects in low-energy nuclear reactions occurring in dense electronic environments, and that neglecting such interference can lead to a systematic misidentification of the observed enhancement as a purely screening-driven effect. The observed enhancement cannot be uniquely decomposed into a simple screening contribution and a bare-nucleus resonance term without an explicit amplitude-level treatment that includes interference effects. Future measurements with improved energy resolution below 10 keV, and in targets with controlled electronic properties, would provide direct tests of this picture and allow a systematic comparison of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ values across different reaction systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author thanks K. Czerski for stimulating discussions. This work was supported by Eskisehir Osmangazi University and TÜBİTAK.

-
- [1] A. M. Boesgaard, C. P. Deliyannis, and A. Steinhauer, *Astrophys. J.* **621**, 991 (2005).
 - [2] A. Cvetinović *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. C* **97**, 065801 (2018).
 - [3] M. Wiescher, R. J. deBoer, and J. Görres, *Front. Phys.* **10**, 1009489 (2022).
 - [4] J. Okołowicz, M. Płoszajczak, and W. Nazarewicz, *Phys. Rev. C* **107**, L021305 (2023).
 - [5] C. Angulo *et al.*, *Z. Phys. A* **345**, 231 (1993).
 - [6] M. Youn *et al.*, *Nucl. Phys. A* **533**, 321 (1991).
 - [7] A. Cacioli *et al.*, *Eur. Phys. J. A* **52**, 136 (2016).
 - [8] B. Vande Kolk *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. C* **105**, 055802 (2022).
 - [9] C. Spitaleri *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. C* **90**, 035801 (2014).
 - [10] R. E. Tribble, C. A. Bertulani, M. La Cognata, A. M. Mukhamedzhanov, and C. Spitaleri, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **77**, 106901 (2014).
 - [11] J. H. Kelley *et al.*, *Nucl. Phys. A* **880**, 88 (2012).
 - [12] A. M. Mukhamedzhanov, *Phys. Rev. C* **108**, 054603 (2023).
 - [13] H. J. Assenbaum, K. Langanke, and C. Rolfs, *Z. Phys. A* **327**, 461 (1987).
 - [14] C. Rolfs and W. S. Rodney, *Cauldrons in the Cosmos* (University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1988).
 - [15] P. Descouvemont and D. Baye, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **73**, 036301 (2010).
 - [16] A. I. Kilic, preprint, doi:10.5281/zenodo.19931932 (2026); submitted to *Phys. Rev. C*.
 - [17] A. I. Kilic and F. K. Kustan, *Mod. Phys. Lett. A* **34**, 1950234 (2019).
 - [18] A. M. Lane and R. G. Thomas, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **30**, 257 (1958).
 - [19] K. Czerski *et al.*, *Europhys. Lett.* **113**, 22001 (2016).
 - [20] A. Huke *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. C* **78**, 015803 (2008).
 - [21] C. Angulo and P. Descouvemont, *Nucl. Phys. A* **690**, 755 (2001).